

**A CROSS EXAMINATION OF AFRICAN AESTHETICS: NIGERIAN
POPULAR MUSIC AS CASE STUDY**

Philo Igue OKPEKI

Department of Music,
Delta State University, Abraka
ndoeyopbennet@gmail.com
0000-0003-3634-3753

&

Oje, Tosin ELIJAH

Department of Theatre Arts,
University of Maiduguri,
Borno State, Nigeria
ojetosin@unimaid.edu.ng,
elijahoje2003@gmail.com
ORCID: 0000-0001-7322-9197

Abstract

This study examines aesthetics in the African context. Nigerian popular music is used as a template to pilot the study. Effort is made to investigate Nigerian popular music by grouping it into two eras based on genres and time-popular music in the colonial era to the early post-colonial era (1940s–1980s) and the contemporary Nigerian popular music (late 1980s–till date). Elements that define African music as good and pleasant to the senses are established vis-a-vis the disparity between a good music and music that is pleasant both in content and context. The research employs content analysis and literary methodologies. This study reveals that what is considered as beautiful is relative across cultures. The paper concludes that both the tangible and intangible aspects of an object must be carefully considered in defining African aesthetics.

Keywords: Aesthetics, African music, Nigerian music, popular music

Résumé

Cet article examine l'esthétique dans le contexte africain. La musique populaire nigériane est le modèle d'orientation dans cette étude. On enquête la musique populaire nigériane en la regroupant en deux époques sur la base des genres, de l'époque coloniale jusqu'au début de l'ère postcoloniale (1940-1980) et la période contemporaine (fin 1980s jusqu'à présent). Des éléments qui déterminent si la

musique africaine est bonne et agréable s'établissent face à la disparité entre une bonne musique et une musique agréable en termes de son contenu et son contexte. La recherche utilise une analyse de contenu et des méthodologies littéraires. Cette étude montre que ce qui est considéré comme bon est relatif d'une culture à l'autre. L'article conclut que les aspects tant tangibles qu'immatériels d'un objet doivent être soigneusement pris en compte dans la définition de l'esthétique africaine.

Mots clés: Esthétique, musique africaine, musique nigériane, musique populaire

Introduction

Aesthetics as a branch of philosophy is concerned with the appreciation of beauty, artistic impact, or appearance. Suru (2008) makes us understand that “it deals with those responses to natural objects and the judgement of them whether they should be regarded as beautiful or ugly” (p. 3). Beauty is the combination of qualities that delight the senses. The 7th Edition of the *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* defines beauty as “the quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind” (p.765). The senses are faculties whereby the human body responds to external stimuli. The generally known human senses that are taught in Basic Sciences and Biology are sight (eyes), smell (nose), hearing (ears), taste (tongue), and touch (skin). There is no gainsaying therefore that these senses could be used as aesthetic senses but they are not exhaustive in differentiating aesthetics in totality.

Other elements that are used to perceive the beautiful are essentially culturally defined. For instance, some of the Western parameters used in selecting the most beautiful lady in any beauty contest are, a lady that is tall, slim and fair in complexion, having straight (hot) legs, sexy eyes, moderate breasts and buttocks, eloquent in speech (English language or the pertinent language), white teeth, charisma, boldness and intelligence. All these qualities a winner must possess can easily be recognised using the basic human senses except, intelligence. This connotes therefore that, other qualities that can easily be identified except intelligence are tangibles while intelligence is intangible. This is because one cannot decipher whether a person is intelligent or not with the aid of mere eyes. It takes extra effort to unearth people's intelligence. However, this could be achieved either through verbal or non-verbal interaction. The questions that emanate in this study are, what sums up the aesthetic? What inform the combinations of the qualities that appeal to one's senses of aesthetic? Are there universal rules or parameters used in judging what is beautiful or otherwise? How do we come about the parameters for judging what is beautiful or ugly?

A Survey of African Concept of Aesthetics

The yardstick for assessing the beautiful in Africa differs from that used in the West. This stems from cultural differences. Suru (2008) submits that “aesthetic values vary from one culture to another, that attracts different interpretations. Africans especially the Yoruba in the Western Nigeria, have qualification or compliment for virtually every physical feature of a lady” (p. 67). Paradigmatically, in Yoruba culture, a dark complexion person is called *duduyemi*, a fair coloured lady is *aponb’epo re*, a slim person is *opelenge*, a plump or chubby person is *alomilara*, someone with sexy eyes is *eleyinjuege*, a tall person is called *aguntaso lo*, a short human being is *akuruyejo*, someone with a white set of teeth is known as *eyin fun’ jowo*, someone with a sexy hip is an *ibadiaran* and someone with a warm smile is called *elerin eye*.

All of the above phrases are complimentary for physical appearance of a lady which therefore suggests that, Africans do not have a specific or standard yardstick that is generally accepted in selecting a beautiful lady based on physical appearance as all of the afore-mentioned represent beauty in African concept of aesthetics. Suggestively, “African concept of aesthetics is intended not only to please the eyes but also, it is meant to uphold moral values” (Suru, 2008, p.1). Also, Okot (1986) corroborates this position by presenting the Acholi of Uganda as a people who uphold a high sense of morality, goodness or kindness, and physical features in judging if someone is beautiful. One could then state that African concept of aesthetics is best expressed in the covert than in the overt form as Africans lay emphasis on the intangibles like good character (*iwa* or *isee* in Yoruba) which “informs good morals that are culturally defined and expressed with different cultural elements. In his study of the aesthetic in Urhobo culture in Southern Nigeria, Okpadah (2016) articulates “what is most important in the categorization of the beautiful is one’s attitude to life. While vice is seen as ugly, uprightness is considered beautiful” (p. 567). Also, for the Yoruba people, virtue is beauty. Other constituents of beauty include good character (*Iwarere /iwa to dara*), calm in character, (*Iwa tutu/iwajeje /iwapele*), patience (*Suuru*), courtesy (*Oni tiju*), temperance (*Ifarada*) and love (*Ife*).

The above and many more are considered crucial in defining whether someone is beautiful or not in African concept of aesthetic aside from the physical qualities. Yoruba aphorisms such as *Iwarerelesoomoeniyan* (human ornament is good character), *Iwalewa* (good character is beauty), *Eefinniwa* (one’s character is like smoke), *Iwarereniyiomoeniyan* (a worth of a person lies in his/her good character), *Obirinso’wa nu*, *onihunolorioko* (a lady lacks virtues; she says she has no suitor) are all examples used to stress the importance of character or morality in defining beauty. Suru (2008) opines that “beauty is a child of morality

in the Yoruba concept of aesthetics” (p.170). Hence, in Africa, aesthetic sense of judgement is mainly placed on the uses and functions of an object that are expressed mostly in performance of that object than in its physical appearance. Suru’s position is limited because, if only the content of the object is used to assess the beautiful, then there would be nothing such as beauty in the real sense of it without paying keen attention to its total make-up which comprises both the tangible as well as the intangible.

The above notwithstanding, it is important to note that, “beauty in Africa is more than the physical because it is encapsulated spiritually, morally, and culturally” (Suru 2008, p. 169). Haruna Ishola one of the exponents of *Apala* music in one of his songs *Ina ran*, talks about how Africans hold of high esteem good virtues (morals) alongside physical qualities in judging a woman’s beauty. Below is one of his songs.

T’obirinbadarati o n’iwa,	if a woman is pretty without virtue,
T’obagba kobo kan abo mi o le fe	and her worth is as cheap as one and half kobo, I still cannot marry her
T’obirinban’iwa tutu t’otunrewa,	if a woman is calmly and pretty,
Mo le fi 1,000 fe	I can marry her with one thousand
(kobo/naira)	

The above song was released in the late 1960s and it shows how Africans cannot compromise good morals for only physical beauty as physical qualities can fade away but the combination of physical qualities with virtues make a perfect beauty. Also, Beautiful Nubia among other contemporary popular musicians in one of his songs *What a feeling*, makes good use of Yoruba complimentary for good character and as well physical quality to express his feeling of love.

Omo to n’iwat’osil’ewa o –	a well cultured and pretty lady
Omoon’iwa tutu yi o –	this calmly behaved lady
Nkoriiruerineyiri o oooh –	I’ve never seen such smile before

From Beautiful Nubia’s lyrics presented above, it is clear that Africans consider both the tangible and the intangible qualities in judging the aesthetic.

An Exploration of African Music Aesthetics

Apart from addressing African concept of aesthetics within the cultural perspective, there abounds what is called a good performer(s) in respect to the quality of his or her voice in the Yoruba society. Mensa (2011) states that:

There are terms used to describe the quality of music performed by any artiste or a group of artistes. Such terms like ‘ohuniyo’ (the voice of salt) means ‘sweet voice’, ‘ohungooro’ (smooth voice) means sonorous voice, ‘ohunaro’ (tremulant voice) means vibrato voice which is most suitable for the rendition of mournful songs. An artiste who possesses any of these voice qualities is described as Olohuniyo, Olohungooro, Olohunaro, as the case maybe (p. 209).

African values, principles, and beliefs which sum up the African concept of beauty also reflect in the indigenous African music. For instance, among the Yoruba people of Nigeria, the word /dun/ sweet or sweetness or pleasant and /da or dara/ good, are used in appreciating performance of any music by the listeners or audience. Examples of the usage of these words in statement are:

Orin yi dun	-	this music is sweet or pleasant
Orin yida’a	-	this music is good
Ohun to dun	-	sweet voice
Ohun to dara	-	good voice

These two words /dun and dara/ are often used interchangeably but there are slight differences in their meaning in relation to the content and context of the word in African music. Music could be good /da/ but not sweet or pleasant /dun/ in the sense that, a song may have good lyrics (content) but if not properly rendered and accompanied with the right instrumentation, may mar the sweetness of the music. The sweetness of African music therefore lies on the holistic performance of the music which encompasses the pleasantness of the voice /ohun to dun/, instrumentation (ajosepohuneloorin), song arrangement (ti to orinpapo), song presentation (agbekale orin), and other multi-media elements that include dance, drama, costume and props. These are what observers, listeners or audience focus on in judging the sweetness of music. Nketia (2005) states that”

Because a musical performance may have visual and movement aspects in the form of costumes, props, and dance, gestures and some form of orderly presentation, it can be described as beautiful when such aspects predominate or form the focus of the observer’s attention. A performance without such visual emphasis is not normally described as beautiful, since music is appraised not just in terms of its apparent surface structures, but more especially in terms of the impact it makes through such structures or the intensity of feeling it generates (p. 32).

The /da/ centres on the societal values based on the culture and custom of the people as expressed by Kwabena Nketia that, the concept of beauty is also linked to morality, for beauty is something to be admired as well as something to acquire. The foregoing expression implies that music which is said to be sweet may as well not be good /da/ if it does not conform to the values of the people that listened to and watched it. Murungi (2011) elaborates that “an African musician is a man or woman of the people. It is from the people that he or she derives his or her Africanness and from whom he or she derives his or her musicality. In isolation from the people, he or she is not what he or she is, and is unintelligible.” (Akpabot, 1986, p. 56). In the light of Akpabot’s position, Nketia (2005) states that “aesthetic principles, ideas, values and behaviours are developed in the context of the society and culture and are related not only to types of music that each society or social group cultivates, but its values system, concept of reality, and the fundamental needs or goals it seeks to fulfil through music” (p. 54). This therefore means that, both the good /da/ and sweetness or pleasantness /dun/ as the case may be of African music should be put into consideration by the musicians in other to have a music performance that is worthwhile and acceptable by the people. That which operates within the construct of time and space and the performer/audience relationship (Okam 2009, p. 38).

Analysis of Nigerian Popular Music and Aesthetics

To examine Nigerian popular musical aesthetics, it is imperative we periodize it. Hence, we shall consider grouping Nigerian popular music based on genres and time into two which are Nigeria’s popular music of the colonial era to the early postcolonial era (1940s–1980s) and the contemporary Nigerian popular music (late 1980s–till date). This is done in order to examine the notable features, transition and shifts in the Nigerian popular music aesthetics which has not been static in order to maintain quotidian relevance in the face of global musical aesthetics. The musical genres in each of these periods are considered in relation to their common distinctive features as well as the musical aesthetics therein. Nigerian popular musical genres of the 1940s–1980s include *Palm-wine*, *Agidigbo*, *Asiko*, *Highlife*, *Juju*, *Reggae*, *Afrobeat*, *Apala*, *Sakara*, *Waka*, *Dadakuada* and *Fuji*. The distinctive and common features as well as aesthetics of the genres are grossly itemized and examined below:

This era encouraged music apprenticeship and mentorship because music was seen as a craft or trade that needed to be taught. This was easy because of the music bands that were common. Anybody who was interested in becoming a musician started by joining a band thereafter, the learning process began which was often by observation, learning how to play a musical instrument, being a

backup singer and later, a lead singer or band leader as the case may be. It would be strange to see any musician of this era not being able to play at least one musical instrument because most of them actually passed through a period of apprenticeship under at least one musician.

Furthermore, this period was predominately known for live band performances that comprised at least three musicians playing certain instruments or singing with a band leader or lead singer. This kind of performance allows for natural creativity, improvisation and thorough composition of musical piece as different experts would assert their creative ingenuity. The audience therefore appreciated music in its natural state where virtually every musical sound heard is played live without using synthesiser. In the era, the themes essentially centred on socio-political issues, religious, commemoration, satirical, and love.

In the same vein, preference is given to musical text (lyrics) in the sense that, the lyrics are carefully selected, they are poetic and loaded with philosophical statements and driven by motivation, value and culture. Most musicians of this epoch are very much in tune with their roots (culture and traditional background) which makes it easier to represent all these in their music and therefore makes their audience to patronise and appreciate the musicians not only because of the music they perform, but also based on the extra musical value or function their music performs which further confirms or reveals that the music is rooted in the traditions and values of the society the musicians leave in. Songs of this era are mostly referred as evergreen in the sense that they are still much relevant to the contemporary age. Musicians of this era include: Mike Okri, Bongos Ikwue, Osita Osadebe, Victor Olaiya, Rex Lawson, I.K Dairo, Ebenezer Obey, Sunny Ade, Orlando Owoh, Ayinla Omowura, Sikiru Ayinde Barrister, Fela Anikulapo Kuti among others.

The music tempo of this period is relatively slow and moderate which also suggest the dance steps that accompanied it. This category of music is now referred as the elder's music; it brings about nostalgic feeling whenever it is played. The instrumentation and orchestration of these musical genres are fusion of indigenous or traditional with foreign musical instruments. According to Ogisi (2005), "the musical genres except *highlife* are mostly performed outside like in an open air space, field, village square or compound" (p. 166). *Highlife* is mostly performed in the dance halls, theatres, night clubs and so on with a prototype of the Western-type stages, where people have to pay to watch a performance.

The second era of Nigerian music-contemporary popular music (late 1980s – till date) is omnibus. Music in this era include: Nigerian *Hip-hop*, *Raps*, *Afro hip-hop*, *Gospel*, *Gospel Juju*, *Fuji*, *Galala*, and so on. One of the common features

of the Nigerian contemporary popular music vis-a-vis its aesthetics is that most of the songs are recorded and mixed in the music studio. According to Omojola (2006), these kind of music “is referred to as ‘frozen’ which is the opposite of ‘live music’ that engages various professional musicians playing together for a performance outside music studio” (p. 202). The studio recording helps in reducing errors which may occur during live performance or outside recording as most of the errors are corrected through editing, cropping and mixing in the studio by the engineer before the master copy is released for mass production.

In addition, the predominant themes of music of this era are on: love, free styling (without specific song theme, mostly filled with slangs and creolised words), religious, and socio-political issues. Bulk of the contemporary Nigerian popular music themes centre on wild affection, sex and alcoholism which are very common to *Hip-hop* and *Rap* among other contemporary popular musical genres. Musical shows in this era are performed both in an open air arena and halls. Basically, *Hip-hop* and *Rap* are performed in enclosed places that include dance halls, theatres, and night clubs. Some others can be performed either in open air space, fields, halls or even church as in the case of Gospel music.

The music instrumentation is essentially generated through synthesiser and electronic keyboard. “The synthesizer and the electronic keyboard, being the latest technological advancement in the music industry, are so versatile and powerful in performance. A good keyboardist can easily produce a track with the synthesizer or keyboard instrument single-handedly” (Agu 2011, p. 16). The introduction of these instruments help musicians in achieving accuracy in terms of rhythm, instrumentation and effects thereby reducing the stress of forming and maintaining live band members to a one or two-man band. Although, some musicians of these genres still include musical instruments other than the synthesizer and keyboard which could either be indigenous or foreign to their music.

Musicians of this age attach more importance to the creation of danceable rhythms which are often fast and complex to meet the yearnings of the youth in particular. Since clubbing, partying and celebration of all kinds are in vogue, creation of danceable beats with fascinating instrumentation which can fit in to almost all occasion, celebration and parties, has become essential. “Today, content doesn’t sell in music, ‘beats’ do. A large junk of what we listen to as music are products of energetic dissipation of empty sounds. Only few musicians are trying to keep up with trend of the legends... every nonsense now makes sense as long as the beat is danceable” (Anibeze et al 2014, p. 30). Thus, musicians concentrate less on going through the painstaking way of composing

philosophical lyrics but on 'hot' and captivating instrumentation spiced with slangs and different styles of dance to quench the thirst of their fans. Could this have amounted to the short life span of most of the music produce in this age? Well, this may not be totally correct as there may be other factors responsible for this too.

A good number of the musicians of this age are multi-talented, but lack certain musicianship qualities simply because most of them do not undergo the painstaking process of apprenticeship and the use of live band performance is not as common as it was in the former era. A 'one-man show' is what is common now especially with *Hip-hop* and *Rap* artistes where they mime their recorded songs on stage. Confluence of hybridity in contemporary popular music, as a reflection of the concept of hybridity-that is neither here nor there as in post-colonial realities is evident in the lyrical formation of contemporary Nigerian popular music which has resulted into creolization of new words and meanings.

Conclusion

Aesthetics in the African context differs from the Western conception of the term. The tangible and intangible facets of an object or subject as the case may be must be carefully considered in defining African aesthetics. Elements that define African music as good and pleasant to the senses are established vis-a-vis the disparity between a good music and music that is pleasant both in content and context. This study reveals that what is considered as beautiful is relative across cultures. The paper concludes that both the tangible and intangible aspects of an object must be carefully considered in defining African aesthetics.

References

- Agu D.C. (2011). The Impact of Electronic Technology on Indigenous and Pop Music: The Nigerian Experience. *Journal of the Association of Nigerian Musicologists*. (5): 16-22
- Akpabot S.E. (1986). *Foundation of Nigerian Traditional Music*. Ibadan: Spectrum Book Ltd.
- Anibeze O, L Arenyeka, J Ebirim, A, and Adeyeri, A. *Today, Content doesn't Sell in Music, 'Beats' do*. Retrieved 5th May, 2017 from www.vanguardngr.com/2014/11/today-content-doesnt-sell-music-beats/
- Emielu A. (2009). Issues in the Revival and Sustenance of Highlife Music in Nigeria. *LASU Journal of Humanities*. (6): 29-38.

- Kotarba J.A, B Merrill, J.P Williams, and P Vannini. (2013). *Understanding Society through popular music*. New York and London: Routledge.
- Mensa E.O. (2011). *Lexicalization in Nigerian Pidgin*. Lagos: Concentric.
- Nketia K. (2005). *Ethnomusicology and African Music*. Ghana: Afram Publications Ltd.
- Ogisi A.A. (2005). The Origin and Development of Juju and Highlife Music 1900–1990. *Journal of the Institute of African Studies*. Vol. 29 No. (1&2):165-186.
- Okon, C. L. (2009). Performer as Enterprise: The Calabar Carnival of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Mukabala Journal of Performing Arts and Culture*. Vol 1, N0 1, June. 37-55
- Okpadah, S. (2016). Aesthetic language of communication in Urhobo culture. In: K. Eni, B. Binebai, S. Ikibe (eds), *Music Scholarship, culture and performance challenges in 21st century Africa: A critical resource book in honour of Emurobome Idolor*. (pp. 566-575). Lagos: Bahiti and Balila Publishers.
- Omojola B. (2006). *Popular Music in Western Nigeria: Theme, Style and Patronage System*. Ibadan. IFRA, Gold Press Ltd.
- Omojola, B. (2012). Yoruba Popular Music: Hybridity, Identity, Power. In: B. Omojola (ed.), *Yoruba Music in the Twentieth Century: Identity, Agency and Performance Practice*. (pp. 162-203). USA: University of Rochester Press.
- Suru D.S. (2008). The African Aesthetics and the Performing Arts. *The Performer: Ilorin Journal of the Performing Arts*. (10): 169-179.